

SUGAR FACTORY DATABASE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

It is software, which manages all the work related to storing and retrieving of individual data into computer. It will create an interface between the storage device and the data-inserting user. It will enable the user to manipulate stored data.

In the day-to-day work, a sugar factory database system needs to store the data like farmer information, bill information etc. This is normally done by accountants in the sugar factory. It will also provide the forms for new member. Sometimes few reports are needed for checking or submitting the tasks done.

I.INTRODUCTION

We all know about management. Management means keeping data in well manner. In sugar factory database management our project is related to managing data for sugar factory related information. About farmer Information, Sugar cane information, Billing information etc.

This software case full for any Sugar factory. This software is used for authorized person only. Like high level person. This high level person uses this software by login_Id and password for secure data for security purpose.

This software start with the login_Id and password is given by high level person like manager.

II.PROPOSED WORK

To make simpler job for accountant to keep the detail records of member and all details of his bill. To keep the records of members like his basic, sugar cane, loan, bill information's. To create information of the new member .To give the printed receipt of bill to the factory member.

III.DIAGRAM

VI. CONCLUSION

Hence, we studied the working process of Sugar Factory and we implemented automatic billing it gives the information of farmer, loan, sugarcane, bill, receipt.

VIII. REFERENCES

Complete Reference java.
Balguruswami book for java
www.wikipedia.com
www.w3schools.com
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